

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Economic performance of different types of green manure in organic arable production depends on their source and on the cultivated crop

Green manure is a sustainable alternative for chemical fertilizers. It increases C-content and improves soil structure. Fermented organic waste additionally improves microbial diversity and activity to produce natural antibiotics, essential vitamins and plant growth hormones. It further improves soil quality and makes it more resilient against pests and diseases. In Belgium, ILVO and Pomona tested different sources of green manure in organic spelt (2021-'22) and potato (2023):

- Cattle farmyard manure (FYM),
- Compost (COM),
- Fermented organic matter (bokashi, grass clover silage) (FOM),
- No fertilization (NONE).

Results

Direct costs for COM and FOM were higher than for FYM and NONE. Both the products themselves and the fuel and labour costs were higher. FOM application was most expensive, as its spreading was most labour intensive.

Potato yields were higher after COM and FOM fertilization, than after FYM or NONE, which resulted in higher revenues. Despite higher costs for COM and FOM, the higher revenues lead to higher gross margins after fertilization with COM or FOM. The largest gross margin was obtained with COM.

In spelt, however, no clear yield differences were found between the treatments. As costs were higher for COM and FOM, and in this case even higher than the revenue obtained for the spelt, both treatments resulted in a negative gross margin. For FYM and NONE the gross margin for spelt was slightly positive.

Conclusion

COM and FOM were more expensive forms of fertilization than FYM. Effects on yield were not uniform. For potato yields were increased, but not for spelt. Whether or not the higher costs are acceptable thus depends on the crop cultivated. These experiments should be repeated to clarify impact on yield.

1. Revenue, direct cost and gross margin (euro/ha) per growth season / crop and the totals over the two year trial

KEYWORDS

Economic profitability, gross margin, compost, bokashi, organic, potato, spelt

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